

A Connected Future for Automated Driving

AT A GLANCE

Design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure to enable higher levels of automation

ICT elements

HYBRID CONNECTIVITY

DATA MANAGEMENT

CYBERSECURITY

DATA PRIVACY

ACCURATE LOCALISATION

Test sites

Test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy

Cross border interoperability at the Italian-Austrian border

Facts and figures

21 Partners

9 EU Countries

36 months duration

10.2M EUR total budget

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ICT4CART

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- High-value use cases, demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions
 - Hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies are integrated under a flexible “sliced” network architecture
 - Seamless integration between all actors from 3 different industries

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION:

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